

CABRISS

NEWSLETTER

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www.spire2030.eu/cabriss

Welcome to the third newsletter of CABRISS project!

CABRISS implements a pioneering approach towards a PV circular economy demonstrating the re-usability and recyclability of key PV materials for PV and other applications like electronics, metallurgy and glass industries.

UPCOMING: STANDARDIZATION WORKSHOP

Save the date: TU Vienna is happy to welcome you for the CABRISS Standardization Seminar. The workshop is free of charge and it will be held at TU Wien Campus Getreidemarkt 9, 1060 Wien, TutheSky, 11th floor, Wednesday, December 07th, 2016, 12:00 – 16:00

CABRISS - Implementation of a Circular economy Based on Recycled, reused and recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver materials for photovoltaic and other applications

H2020-WASTE-2014

Starting date: June 1st, 2015

Project duration: 36 months

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HORIZON 2020

Overview

- CABRISS Standardisation workshop and activities 2
- Report on economic opportunities and markets for PV waste 4
- CABRISS – Work in progress 7

STANDARDIZATION WORKSHOP

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Integrating research with standardisation has a number of advantages for researchers, businesses, and for society. Standards can form the foundations for further developments, new research and ultimately new knowledge, creating a virtuous knowledge circle for standards and research. It is becoming increasingly important to integrate research results into standards, as well as establish new areas of standards activities. This leads to better standards and creates the potential for new business opportunities for European companies. The seminar will be held by Ms. Andreea Gulacsi Gologan. She will share her valuable experience as a Research Integration Unit Manager at the CEN and CENELEC - European Standardization Committee. Her key areas of work are coordinating and

facilitating the link between standardization and research, providing support to the CEN and CENELEC members engaged with Horizon2020 and to research projects to address standardization in their proposals and projects.

The seminar aims at helping researchers and businesses to understand the role of standardization in innovation and to address related questions at an early stage in the development process, thereby supporting market uptake and exploitation. (*CEN – EU Committee for Standardization/ CENELEC - EU Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization /www.cencenelec.eu*).

For information, agenda and registration (participation is free of charge), please contact Werner.Brenner@tuwien.ac.at.

Additional information can be found on the project website: www.spire2030.eu/cabriiss.

STANDARDIZATION

Standardization within CABRISS aims at providing a bridge that connects research to industry. This is of importance as investors in new technologies have to overcome the critical phase between demonstration and commercialization. To cross this well-known “valley of death”, a good awareness and understanding of all pre-requirements for accessing the market is crucial.

Two technology steps are addressed in CABRISS:

- collection of end-of-life modules, cells and PV waste
- dismantling, extraction and recovery

Both are strongly influenced by the European directive WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Directive) which became effective on 14th February 2014. WEEE regulates the treatment of electrical and electronic waste at the end of life cycle.

The Commission requested the European standardization organizations to develop standards for the recycling treatment, including separation and removal of key components, such as frames, glass, polymers, plastics and metals, including cables. Among these organisations, CABRISS has established contacts to SEMI and CEN/CENELEC for a closer interaction and knowledge exchange.

Meanwhile, CABRISS has deepened collaboration with CENELEC’s CLC/TC 111X Environment (prEN 50625-2-4) which deals with collection, logistics and treatment requirements for WEEE- part2-4: „Specific requirements for the treatment of photovoltaic panels“. In September 2016, the chair of TC111X invited the CABRISS consortium to comment the draft documents which are expected to be available in November 2016.

On 10th November 2016, CABRISS was presented to CENELEC’s CLC/TC 111X in Brussels during the plenary meeting.

WASTES FROM SILICON PV MANUFACTURING AND THEIR ECONOMIC VALUE

The CABRISS project aims at providing new technologies and new insights that support a circular economy for the PV sector. To elucidate the economic environment, the project plan foresees one deliverable focusing on a thorough market and competitive analysis. The following chapter presents parts of the analysis.

A number of wastes are generated during the PV cell production process and some of these wastes can be recycled both in and outside of the PV industry. Today, the two main wastes that are recycled within the production process are the silicon off-cuts that are created when cutting either the cast multi-crystalline silicon or the monocrystalline ingot. Much of this high-quality silicon can readily be recycled within ingot manufacturing and therefore represents closed-loop recycling at this point in the value chain. The second recycling process that is currently used in the industry involves slurry recycling.

Whereas ingot block cutting creates silicon waste of generally very high quality that can be easily recycled within ingot manufacture, the wafering process creates large quantities of silicon kerf (powder) loss as the result of cutting the ingots into thin (today 180 micron thick) wafers. The wafering step leads to approximately a 45% loss of silicon volume, and this volume is either in the form of dry powder, in the case where cutting uses a diamond saw, is the form of silicon powder mixed with the abrasive (silicon-carbide based) cutting slurry in the case of traditional steel wire cutting.

Other potential wastes for recycling come from cell and module manufacture, including final installation. During cell processing, we can define three main stages at which the wafer can potentially be recycled. If the wafer is broken early on before processing has begun, it can “easily” be resold to the ingot/wafer maker for re-melting and reintroduction into the process of ingot manufacture. In the case that cell processing has begun, but before the stage of latter stages of metallization, the cell can be processed through a series of chemical cleaning and lapping stages again returned for ingot manufacture (assuming such a process makes economic sense for the cell maker). In the third situation, in which either a breakage occurs after metallization has begun (or the final cell is simply not within specification) the cell is much more difficult to recycle, but falls into the scope of CABRISS, in the sense that the silicon and the silver can in principal be recovered and used either inside or outside of PV applications. For modules broken during the production process, the aluminium frame may be easily recoverable for immediate reuse, but panels broken during the installation process are very similar to end-of-life panels from a recycling perspective.

The figure below summarizes the recycling potential (the focus of CABRISS) including the recycling of silicon kerf from block-cutting, wafering and from broken cells and part-produced modules and silver used in the cell-manufacturing process. Production wastes will clearly be a function of production volumes and therefore wastes from PV production in Europe will be more modest than those in Asia.

Figure 1 Source: CEA. Silicon production flow and losses.

The figures calculated from this material-flow analysis provide some perspective on the current level of silicon waste generated unintentionally in the industry. For every 2.4 g per watt of power that end up in the final panel, 5.1 g were consumed somewhere in the production value chain. Assuming a market of 50 GW and a polysilicon price of \$15 per kilogram for pure solar grade polysilicon, the implied value of the silicon waste is approximately equal to \$2.2 billion per annum globally.

SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC PANELS: END-OF-LIFE MANGEMENT

For further reading, we recommend the report: “End-of-Life Management: Solar Photovoltaic Panels” which was published in June 2016 by the international Energy Agency Photovoltaic Power Systems Program (IEA-PVPS) in collaboration with the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). IEA (www.iea-pvps.org) is an autonomous body within the framework of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) that carries out a comprehensive program of energy co-operation among its member countries. IRENA (www.irena.org) is an intergovernmental organization that supports countries in their transition to a sustainable energy future and serves as the principal platform for international co-operation, a centre of excellence and a repository of policy, technology, resource and financial knowledge on renewable energy. This report represents the first global projection for future PV panel waste volumes to 2050. It highlights that recycled PV represents an opportunity to create and pursue new economic avenues. This study analyses national approaches to PV waste management and lays open volumes of decommissioned PV panels, opportunities for the 3 R’s (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), as well as costs and requirements for an expanded waste management infrastructure.

Keeping track of the work of both institutions (i.e. reflecting the documents they issue) helps to predict the future legal and technological requirements.

The entire report can be found and downloaded via the following link:

http://iea-pvps.org/index.php?id=95&eID=dam_frontend_push&docID=3222

CABRISS WORK IN PROGRESS

The technology development in CABRISS is organised in five workpackages (WPs):

- **WP1** PV Waste collection and dismantling, materials extraction
- **WP2** Purification of silicon recovered in PV wastes
- **WP3** Fabrication of silicon wafers using recycled materials
- **WP4** Fabrication of silicon solar cells using recycled materials
- **WP5** Transformation of recycled materials into usable products

At midterm, WP1 and WP2 have delivered sufficient output to feed the product cycle of the subsequent WPs, while at the same time testing alternative / additional pathways. In the following, we report some current developments from WP3 and WP4.

Growth of ingots from Si scraps

At this stage of the project, the CABRISS partner SINTEF (Norway) is focusing on the growth of multi-Si and Cz Si ingots from any relevant silicon (Si) feedstock which has been provided by partners. In particular, Si scrap-based feedstock is under consideration. In general, Si scrap can consist of: (i) broken wafers, (ii) broken solar cell structures at from different steps of processing, including broken finished solar cells or solar cells that are extracted from end-of-life solar modules. In all cases, all non-Si solar cell-base related layers (metallization, antireflection coating, emitter, back surface field) have to be etched away and the Si feedstock obtained in this way can be used for the growth of ingots. Such ingots are used for fabrication of Si wafers by wire based cutting (Fraunhofer) followed by Si solar cell processing (Solitek, CEA). An image of a Cz Si ingot (~20 kg) is shown below:

Figure 2 Cz Si ingot (~20 kg) grown from Si scraps.

Transformation of Silicon kerf to ingots

The CABRISS partner RHP (Austria) is looking into the transformation of recycled silicon powder into ingots. As a starting material RHP uses silicon powder that is provided by the project partner RESITEC (Norway). The silicon powder is available in different particle size and was investigated with respect to the densification behaviour using a pressure assisted sintering technique such as hot pressing. One of the goals of RHP is to develop an industrial process which allows a fast transformation of the powders to ingots. To do so, a rapid hot pressing process was applied and investigated. The silicon powders are inserted into a pressing mold which is typically made from graphite. One of the issues to solve was to identify suitable processing conditions that allow to obtain a high densification of >95%. This requires temperatures which are close to the melting point of silicon. Consequently, appropriate protection layers for the graphite tooling have to be studied.

By applying a rapid hot pressing process heating rates of 50-100 Kelvin per minute can be realized. Therefore, the cycle for the ingot processing is significant faster compared to conventional hot pressing. An additional advantage of the used powder metallurgical process is the possibility to tune the electrical conductivity by using doping of the silicon with elements such as boron. First ingots could be processed with a size of 156 mm x 156 mm. The ingots are now tested for multi-wire cutting and subsequent manufacturing of cells.

Figure 3 Left: Pseudo-square ingot with size of 156 mm X 156 mm. Right: Ingot with a height of > 105 mm could be obtained.

UPCOMING: CABRISS M18 PROGRESS MEETING

The internal Month 18 CABRISS progress meeting will be held from 8th to 9th December 2016 at the Technische Universität Wien, Austria.